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1. Introduction

The LIFE WEELOOP project proposes a holistic management system for Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), based on circular economy principles. It focuses on the recovery of materials and components from kitchen hobs (induction, radiant, and hybrid), targeting a recovery rate of up to 90%. This approach incorporates advanced technologies and methodologies to support eco-design, facilitate the extraction and separation of valuable materials, and reduce reliance on virgin resources and non-EU suppliers.

As part of the monitoring and evaluation framework of the project, this document presents the first KPI report linked to the LIFE KPI webtool. The report compiles the set of Key Performance Indicators defined for the project, grouped according to environmental, technical, and economic impact categories. It also provides an overview of the methodological approach adopted for their definition, laying the groundwork for future comparisons between estimated and achieved values. This initial version focuses on KPI structuring and systematisation, prior to the full deployment of data collection and analysis in the following reporting periods.

2. Report Overview and Methodological Approach

This report is part of the monitoring activities of the LIFE WEELOOP project and is aligned with the reporting requirements set by the European Commission through the LIFE Programme. Specifically, the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in this document are reported via the LIFE monitoring platform (<https://life-helpdesk-elman.ey-bpm.com/>), using the LIFE Performance Indicators (LPI) tool.

The purpose of this first KPI report is to document the selection, categorisation, and rationale behind the KPIs established for the project. These indicators are designed to measure the environmental, technical, and economic performance of the proposed WEEE management model, ensuring consistent tracking of progress and impact throughout the project's implementation.

The KPIs have been structured to align with the main intervention areas of the project and reflect both direct and indirect outcomes. The methodology used for their definition considers existing LIFE KPI frameworks, specific project objectives, and the data availability expected at each implementation stage. Reported values are organised with reference points “at the beginning,” “at the end,” and “beyond three years” after project completion, allowing for a clear temporal comparison of progress and long-term impact.

Furthermore, KPIs are classified using hierarchical descriptors, including first-level and second-level descriptors, to facilitate structured analysis and clear understanding of indicator categories and their relevance.

This structured approach will facilitate future updates in the LIFE KPI webtool, allowing for a clear comparison between estimated and actual values as data collection progresses.

3. Defined KPI Groups

The LIFE WEELOOP project has established a comprehensive set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) organized into thematic groups, each designed to monitor distinct aspects of the project's performance and impact. These KPI groups reflect the multifaceted nature of the circular economy interventions applied to the management of Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE), specifically kitchen hobs. The groups are aligned with the strategic objectives of the project and the overarching framework of the LIFE Programme's monitoring requirements.

3.1 Environmental Performance Indicators

This group focuses on measuring the environmental benefits derived from the project activities, emphasizing reductions in resource consumption, energy use, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Key indicators include:

- **Primary Energy Consumption Reduction (Indicator 4.1.1):** This KPI quantifies the decrease in primary energy demand through the reuse of induction heaters in kitchen hobs. It calculates energy savings based on the energy needed to manufacture new components versus the negligible energy required for recovery and reuse processes. The indicator uses a conversion factor to translate final energy into primary energy, aligning with LIFE methodology.
- **Circular Economy Metrics (Indicator 4.4):** This set of KPIs measures the volume of WEEE materials prepared for reuse, recycling, and recovery, as well as the portion that cannot be reused or recycled due to losses. The indicators track progress from project start, through end-of-project targets, to expected performance three years after project completion. The efficiency assumptions (90% treatment efficiency) reflect the state-of-the-art standards for WEEE processing.
- **Greenhouse Gas Emissions Reduction (Indicator 8.1):** These indicators estimate the carbon footprint reduction achieved by substituting newly manufactured kitchen hobs with reused units. The methodology accounts for emissions generated during recovery processes and compares them to the emissions associated with new manufacturing, applying a conservative residual emission factor for reuse activities. This group quantifies both absolute emissions avoided and per-unit emissions reductions, supporting the project's climate impact goals.

3.2 Socio-Economic and Stakeholder Engagement Indicators

Recognizing the importance of human and institutional factors, this group monitors the project's social impact and stakeholder involvement:

- **Stakeholder Involvement (Indicator 10.2):** Measures the number of public bodies, specifically municipalities, actively participating in project activities. Engagement of local municipalities is crucial for effective WEEE collection, citizen awareness, and governance of circular economy initiatives.
- **Professional Training and Capacity Building (Indicator 10.3):** Tracks the number of individuals trained in the project's recovery and reuse processes, including workers at NGOs and civil society organizations. This KPI reflects investments in human capital to ensure high-quality operations and the sustainability of circular practices.
- **New Jobs Created (Indicator 13):** Quantifies the creation of full-time equivalent (FTE) jobs within the project consortium and the wider ecosystem, demonstrating the project's contribution to economic development and workforce growth linked to circular economy activities.

3.3 Economic Performance and Scalability Indicators

To evaluate the financial viability and scalability potential of the WEELOOP model, the following KPIs have been defined:

- Revenue Generated (Indicator 14.1): Captures income derived from the commercialization of eco-designed products, reused components, and recycled materials, both during the project and in the years following its completion. This indicator highlights the economic sustainability of the circular business models implemented.
- Catalytic Effect - Financial (Indicator 14.2): Intended to measure investments or external financing triggered by the project's results. For WEELOOP, no additional financial investments beyond the project's own funding are anticipated, and this indicator remains at zero.
- Continuation at Higher Scale (Indicator 14.3.1): Qualitative and quantitative assessment of the project's ability to maintain and expand its activities post-completion, leveraging established partnerships and operational frameworks to scale circular economy solutions.

Communication and Dissemination Indicators

- Website Traffic (Indicator 11.1): Monitors the number of unique visits to the project website, serving as a proxy for outreach effectiveness, stakeholder engagement, and dissemination success.

The validated tables from the first KPI report are attached as [Annex 1](#) for reference and further analysis.

4. Next Steps

The LIFE WEELOOP project will continue progressing with the systematic monitoring and reporting of the established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) throughout the remaining project duration and beyond. Emphasis will be placed on maintaining the methodological approach based on the reporting milestones of at the beginning, at the end, and beyond three years after project completion, to ensure consistent and comparable tracking of project performance and impact.

Ongoing data collection and analysis will support adaptive management and allow timely identification of any deviations from initial targets. This will enable the project consortium to implement corrective actions and optimise the circular economy model's outcomes.

A subsequent deliverable, D7.4 – 2nd KPI Report for LIFE KPI Webtool, is planned for Month 36. This report will provide a comprehensive comparison between the estimated KPIs presented in this initial report and the actual values achieved by the end of the project. It will include an extract of the data uploaded to the LIFE KPI webtool and offer a detailed examination of significant variances encountered during implementation, along with explanations and lessons learned.

This next phase will strengthen the transparency, accountability, and dissemination of project results, supporting replicability and scalability of the WEELOOP approach within the LIFE Programme and beyond.

Annex 1: Verified tables from the first KPI report